

THE STRUCTURE OF URBAN GREENING

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Annotation: This article introduces the study of urban greening, the use of landscape architecture for contemporary aesthetic and environmental purposes, and highlights the strengths and weaknesses of landscape architecture, landscape analysis, and the development of landscape theory.

Key words: Landscape system, landscape architecture, aesthetic and ecological, relief, gardening, ecology, natural.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola shaharlarni ko'kalamzorlashtirish, landshaft arxitekturasidan zamonaviy estetik va ekologik maqsadlarda foydalanishni o'rganish bilan tanishtiradi va landshaft arxitekturasining kuchli va zaif tomonlarini, landshaft tahlilini va landshaft nazariyasining rivojlanishini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: landshaft tizimi, landshaft arxitekturasi, estetik va ekologik, relyef, bog'dorchilik, ekologiya, tabiiy.

Introduction. It is known that architects are engaged not only in the construction of buildings and structures, the creation of cities, but also in the architecture of open spaces and their organization. These include streets, squares, flowerbeds, alleys, beaches, parks within neighborhoods, squares, boulevards, private parks, parks, national parks, alleys, parks, historical landscapes.

The main goal of the urban landscape and landscape architecture is the formation of a compositional artistic, architectural, planning and landscape environment of such open spaces due to natural landscape and artificial elements, including small architectural forms, elements of external improvement and information devices.

Architecture, urban planning and landscape architecture are inextricably linked and differ from each other in the materials and tools used to create the environment. All three spheres served the general direction and purpose in the history of the development of human society.[1]

Material and Methods. Landscape planning issues in Uzbekistan are part of the tum an Planning Scheme. However, the growing problems of Ecology actualize the need for conservation, protection of natural and land resources, as well as the need to deeply study the problems of restoration and unfavorable land development landscape planning of disturbed lands and their allocation to an independent type of professional activity aimed at improving the stability of the environment of the Republic of Uzbekistan. An important role in landscape planning is played by increasing the social, economic, environmental and aesthetic comfort of the environment. The future of parks and squares cannot be accurately assessed without a system of common urban areas. First of all, it is necessary to note the processes of complication of the structure of the high-rise system of green spaces. This is due to the emergence of new elements of regional development of cities and agglomerations. The development of green systems goes in different directions in different cities.

The construction of urban landscaping is determined by urban planning factors (the size and profile of the city, its significance, historical buildings) and natural conditions, climate, soils, existing vegetation, relief, and water bodies. The size of the city affects the composition of green spaces, their size, functional landscape organization. Depending on the location of the residential area, green spaces are divided into five categories:

1-A - green spaces that perform a conservation function, including nature reserves, natural monuments, parts of the sanitary protection of water sources.

2-B - cultural heritage gardens - historical gardens, dendrological, botanical and zoological gardens and parks; memorial cemeteries.

3-D - public parks, city and district parks, squares, squares in squares, pedestrian streets, embankments, suburban recreation areas.

4-E - limited-use parks, micro-district and micro-district parks, parks with individual devices, kindergartens, schools, administrative and other buildings, parks of universities and sports complexes.

5-F - green spaces for special purposes - these are roads, streets, industrial enterprises and their sanitary facilities, nurseries, greenhouses, cemeteries, roads and railways.[1]

The formation of the green spaces of the city - objects of garden and park architecture in different cities took place in different ways. The principles of creating a planting system traditional for the Central Asian region can be considered on the example of the historical cities of Uzbekistan. As can be seen from the figure, all historical cities - Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva - have a flat water supply system - canals, ponds (Fig. 1).

At present, the historical principles of organizing green spaces in the form of a planar layout have been lost. The need for cities to create a flat and continuous system of greenery has already been recognized. Research in the field of landscape architecture and landscape urban planning shows that while maintaining

the relief, landscape solutions should be translated into the implementation of urban planning principles.

City builders need to find and test different, convenient and viable models that, despite the constant changes in external environmental factors, determine the development of the city and its suburbs, on the contrary, intensify without weakening relations with nature, but then in practice. Residential arrays, in particular cities and mainly large cities, consist of islands that bomb various functional areas. These are central, peripheral, industrial, recreational areas, external transport zones, etc.

This territorial landscape organization depends both on a specific functional task and on other factors that determine the specifics of natural, socio-economic, environmental, sanitary and hygienic, urban construction and planning and spatial organization. This is influenced by two groups of Omis based on urban landscape planning; landscape (or natural) and urban construction (functional planning).

Fig 1. The current greenery status of the city of Moscow

For further improvement of the greening system of settlements in Uzbekistan, an architectural basis is needed, providing for a quantitative ratio of the elements of the greening system of urban and rural areas. On the basis of research conducted by the Tashkent Research Institute (TashZNIIP), recommendations have been developed for the regulation of green spaces in Uzbekistan, which can be used as the basis for real practice in design and urban planning.[4]

In parks and forest parks, we see, first of all, an important link in the system of human interaction with the natural environment. The city of the future, the foundations of which are being laid now, should not be opposed to the natural environment, but should be organically integrated with it. The boundaries of the city are losing their ambiguity, and the interaction of buildings and open green spaces is gradually becoming one of the most important principles for the development of the system of cities and settlements.[5]

Conclusion. The largest cities include large forests, vast reservoirs, and hundreds of acres of gardens. They need to preserve all the riches of the natural landscape

and restore them as needed. For nature to relax, it is not necessary to leave the city, it is important to create the opportunity to relax in a natural environment in the bosom of nature near the places of residence, work and study.

However, the conditions for the development of cities, their landscape features, as well as the needs of different groups of urban residents in places and types of recreation are very diverse. They are not the same in residential systems located in certain natural and climatic conditions.

The main goal of landscape design is to create a comfortable spatial environment for a person with all the necessary functional, aesthetic and environmental features. It is based on the purposeful transformation of certain natural landscapes. Therefore, the issues of their identification, classification, structure are of great practical importance not only for theory, but also for architecture.

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